

Stakeholders’ Support and Academic System Optimisation: Interrogating The Issues in Public Universities

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ABSTRACT

The significance of having a viable academic system, particularly at the university level cannot be overstated. This is because apart from enhancing self-confidence in teaching, learning, and research, the skills and knowledge acquired open opportunities for personal career development, social responsibility, and greater prospects of harnessing vital resources for the economic success of the country. Even with the many ambitious educational initiatives designed by government institutions and other key players to guarantee the intended results, there is still much room for improvement in the value that the universities add and create. This paper aims to optimise the benefits of teaching, learning and other mandates of universities, as academic systems, and provide paths that shift from the current narrative to produce desired alternative outcomes. Participant observation as well as systematic desk research were used to raise stakeholders' support concerns in a thematic format to interrogate the issues working against the achievement of academic system optimisation in public universities in Nigeria. It was suggested amongst other things that, resolving the inter-influencing stakeholders' support concerns about important stakeholders such as students, lecturers, institutional policymakers, professional bodies, and society at large, will provide the necessary boost for academic system optimisation.

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INTRODUCTION

University education has shaped critical thinkers who have provided practical solutions to individual, societal and global real-life challenges and will continue to do so as long as sustainable academic systems are in place. A university education is essential to human development and offers the advanced skills required for all job markets. The products of this level of education build the analytical abilities and capacity that propel local economies, uphold civil society, run efficient governments, make critical decisions that impact entire societies and serve as examples for other generations to emulate and sustain. The need for effective service delivery of the outcomes of the academic system as well as the need for educational planning and administration within an entrepreneurship framework for the enhancement of national growth and development have been emphasised (Abdullahia, 2025; Akinyemi & Mohammed, 2023; Asiyai, 2022). Nigeria’s University education premiered in 1948 with the establishment of the University of Ibadan, then University College Ibadan, a College of the University of London. From the initial establishment of five Federal

government-owned universities in 1962, the Nigerian University system as of April 2024 is made of two hundred and seventy-four universities comprising sixty-two Federal government-owned, sixty-three state government-owned, and one hundred and forty-nine privately-owned universities (NUC, 2024). The National Universities Commission (NUC) stipulates the education and training requirements for students desirous of pursuing degrees in core fields of study domiciled in the seventeen approved faculties. The Faculties include “Administration and Management Sciences; Agriculture; Allied Health Sciences; Architecture; Arts; Basic Medical Sciences; Communication and Media Studies; Computing; Education; Engineering and Technology; Environmental Sciences; Law; Medicine and Dentistry; Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences; Social Sciences; and Veterinary Medicine” (NUC,2024). Nigerian university graduates have made significant contributions to nation-building and the creation of knowledge for global research, but much more work needs to be done in the academic system. The goal of university education is to foster unprecedented growth and development for the country in all

spheres of life, both at the local and international levels, as well as in other crucial areas of socioeconomic well-being. The knowledge obtained from the various specialised fields of the university system is essential for the smooth running of all firms and the course equips graduates with requisite skills and critical and analytical thinking, decision-making, and problem-solving in the specialised areas. The graduates from the universities also have the chance to create employment opportunities for the vast unemployed population seeking employment.

Increases in foreign investment in Nigeria require the training of individuals to understand such operations, including fostering beneficial working relationships. International collaborations to engage in scholarly conversations and make useful contributions to global knowledge. Suffice it to say that the optimised university education can significantly improve the quality of teaching and learning, and help students develop a wider range of skills and abilities to manage the various facets of national resources more efficiently.

Thus, it becomes imperative for teaching, learning and other university mandates to effectively occur within these revered educational contexts, there must be mental, emotional, social and physical enabling environments. An optimised academic system is when each university’s outputs are objectively seen to be attaining and even exceeding the objectives and expectations of its establishment. Stakeholder support is the degree to which the influencing parties, structures and norms actively offer faculty and students such conducive environments that allow them to carry out their jobs and succeed academically.

This paper aims to highlight and resolve stakeholders' support concerns about important stakeholders. In this work, the students, lecturers, institutional policymakers, professional bodies, and society at large are regarded as critical stakeholders and integral parts of the university education system. The behavioural exhibitions of each stakeholder though exhibited independently, seem to have implications for the behaviour of others. The focus on public universities is due to the significant majority of the accessible population to these schools as nine of ten university students in Nigeria are in public universities (NUC, 2024).

This work regards stakeholders’ support concerns as culpable clogs in the wheel of progress of academic system optimisation. It is hoped that by interrogating the issues highlighted and with the suggestions offered, their debilitating impacts will be mitigated and the academic systems optimised for economic success.

ISSUES AND PERSPECTIVES AFFECTING ACADEMIC SYSTEM OPTIMISATION

The university academic system has a compelling mandate to have a significantly favourable impact on the lives of

individuals, groups, society and the larger global space as the knowledge acquired is expected to be put to practical use in beneficial ways. Suffice it to say that people make up the academic system and for the system to work in line with the trajectory that achieves the desired mandate, the people’s behavioural displays must align with paths of progress.

While these expectations are high and achievable, it is expedient to note that the compellingly linked concerns of certain stakeholders hinder the optimisation of academic systems. This paper has identified the influences affecting behaviours as emanating from stakeholders such as students, lecturers, institutional policymakers, professional bodies, and society at large. The implications of each stakeholder are intertwined with the other and rather than treat them in isolation of each other, all should be treated as an integrated whole. These salient issues are discussed in this section while pointing out the challenges and suggesting workable, forward-thinking solutions.

THE STUDENTS AS STAKEHOLDERS

Universities are hubs for innovation and research that can aid in the creation of new goods, services, and technology. In addition to being exposed to a wider range of cultures and international concerns, university graduates have greater access to employment options, including higher-paying jobs, leadership roles and liberation from poverty. This makes the attainment of university-level education very desirable for many young people. Over two million candidates apply for admission each year through the Joint Admissions and Matriculation Board's Unified Tertiary Matriculation Examination, but the universities that are currently available can only accept a maximum of seven hundred thousand students as their carrying capacity (JAMB, 2024).

It is important to state that the students are major stakeholders in the academic system. However, the benefits of the academic system are significantly limited by the behavioural disposition of students and the circumstantial situations they face. For example. Some undergraduate students admitted into the Universities display different behavioural demeanours that do not augur well for the students themselves and the academic system as a whole. Some students appear unprepared for the courses being taught. Instead, they merely believe that the degree is a springboard to enter the workforce, get leadership roles in the public and private sectors, venture into other business domains like entrepreneurship, or for the possible financial and social benefits of adding the status symbol of a university graduate to one's profile. These prioritise obtaining a degree over acquiring information and skills. Note that graduates who possess the degrees without the requisite knowledge, will not be able to demonstrate the necessary practice approaches in their unique fields and will not be able to add value from the University system to society. This disposition may be borne out of the societal value placed on wealth and a reflection of the get-rich-quick- syndrome.

Some other students prioritise the acquisition of expert knowledge in their areas of specialisation. These students make efforts to study the contents of stipulated courses and graduate with degrees but the knowledge acquired is at variance with industry and research roles expectations as well as in global organisational practices. This results from a combination of several factors such as the pedagogy; availability of tools, facilities, resources or exposure to practical situations; policies and regulations of University management or national policymakers to mention a few. Some other students may intend to engage in entrepreneurial ventures after school and will have to build the mindset for success in such ventures. The best time to start is while in training but the enabling environment will have to be cultivated. Suffice it to say that the very high rate of graduate unemployment and the highly saturated employment market as well as several of such factors do not only affect the psyche of the students who see no need for education but also confuse, frustrate and discourage students in their quest for knowledge. Several authors have identified such challenges confronting students in public institutions (Eli-Chukwu et al, 2023; Ogunode & Ade, 2023; Omoniyi, 2024).

As practical ways forward which could be done by lecturer support and reiterated by professional bodies and institutional policymakers, there is the need for the general orientation of the students and awareness of students on the huge potential for the proper acquisition of knowledge that will contribute to all spheres of life. Also, as part of the curriculum and pedagogy, the institutional policymakers can formulate a policy that each course should have special selling points. The knowledge acquired from each course should make the student feel like a professional in that course to the extent that such a person will be able to use the knowledge gained from that course to create value in his/her immediate environment and will be able to seek employment and earn income based on that single course. The student should be able to offer amateur services as a self-employed person and obtain reasonable clientele with a reasonable monetary value. This will be assessed and proceeds shared using an agreed ratio. Note that the institutional policymakers will provide the necessary support and funds.

Students should understand that their determination can make things work better. To gain practical knowledge and skills students can be grouped and designated as teams and made to come up with possible workable solutions to real and imagined challenges. Role-playing and real-life volunteering options will give students the requisite work experience while in the university and make them ready to take action when the moment of opportunity comes in the industry or as research experts. Certificate acquisition should be downplayed as a form of reorientation approach while advocating knowledge and skills acquisition in the real sense of it by making students know that in the real world, firms are interested in value creation and delivery as well as the translation of concepts,

principles and theories into practical solutions. All they require are employees’ knowledge and skills to make meaningful contributions to the work and real-life situations. There is no gain in saying that whatever knowledge acquired in the institution should be learned for knowledge transfer and practical application in industry. Students must know the industry needs so that the knowledge acquired can be tailored to meet industry and societal needs and expectations.

The current challenges based on students' disposition should not be treated with mediocre seriousness if valued results of academic system optimisation are to be achieved. There should be a rethinking of the current educational approaches with a huge priority on the ability to utilise skills in practical scenarios for development and enhance competence. The degree should have a direct impact on the life of the graduate and add value in real-life situations. Students should have accessible and compassionate academic advisers as well as counsellors to encourage them to have the right attitudes towards the course being studied. In order to assist students in achieving stability, these counseling platforms might also include mental health and wellbeing services that can build them into character to take up the opportunities that professional life might entail. As young scholars get support from other stakeholders and are exposed to real-world situations through pedagogical approaches such as role-playing, purpose-driven internships, and simulations they understand how best to handle situations when they have the opportunities to meaningfully contribute to the optimisation of the academic system.

THE LECTURERS AS STAKEHOLDERS

The lecturers have the mandate of transferring knowledge to students enrolled for the courses in the various programmes in the universities. It is highly crucial that the intellectual capacity to deliver on the study materials, the pedagogical approaches as well as the mental and emotional state of mind of such a person must be in tip-top shape. Although the actual trajectory of each academic staff may be different and varied as they navigate the long and tortuous journey through careers, all academic staff are periodically assessed on teaching, research, community service as well as administrative experiences. Lecturers are also expected to supervise and mentor students. The challenges faced by lecturers in Nigeria may not be different from other African countries even as they have their unique subtleties (Ajayi, 2024; Jacob, 2024; Mbatha et al, 2020). Many University lecturers in this contextual environment have met and exceeded minimum benchmarks in terms of possessing the qualifications and requirements for performance at universal levels. The products of the universities have also contributed immensely to academic discourse in the global arena. However, a lot more has to be done to continue to obtain the optimum desired level of performance and aspire to greater heights.

In the course of the performance of their duties, it is sometimes observable that some lecturers emotionally transit between mental states of moral identity, self-efficacy and emotional exhaustion, based on the circumstances of the support at work (Hoo et al, 2024; Osilike et al,2024; Uyeri,2024) The mental state affects their emotions, beliefs, perceptions and intentions which can also be used to predict their behaviour. Thus one may sometimes observe the continuum shift from feeling happy to feeling sad. For example, the average lecturer usually has a strong urge to maintain a moral identity which is greatly linked to their personal values and ethical principles. Moral identity is considered a mental state where a person views their morality as central to their self-concept. It is a psychological construct where being a moral person is a key part of one's identity and acts as a significant motivator for moral behaviour (Laiho et al, 2022; Yang et al, 2022). This lack of continuous training and professional development alongside the use of the latest tools and techniques makes individual lecturers question their level of self-efficacy. Self-efficacy is considered a mental state which relates to an individual's conviction in their capacity to complete a task or reach a target. In essence, it is a cognitive perception of one's capabilities rather than an objective reality, making it a mental construct that affects behaviour and decision-making. Avoiding challenging activities, procrastinating, giving up quickly, viewing obstacles as threats, having low expectations, and being readily overcome by unpleasant emotions are some indicators of low self-efficacy (Edokpolor et al,2022; Mohammed et al,2024; Musa et al,2024). A tip to achieving positive self-efficacy is to keep believing in oneself and resorting to self-help at professional development and hoping to get a good payoff to help one's mental state.

Trying to convince unwilling students to learn course content, especially when the teaching tools and aids are unavailable could be emotionally exhausting. Emotional exhaustion is a mental state that makes the lecturer feel drained and worn out emotionally (Goga et al, 2023; Ilonze, 2024; Oderinde et al, 2024). Just thinking of the low purchasing power of the pay alongside the workload could also make the person irritable and struggle with concentration and motivation, increasing rates of absence from work, and a lack of enthusiasm which are also signs of emotional exhaustion.

Apart from the foregoing, lecturers may tend to face other challenges and exhibit behaviours which are not in line with patterns that lead to academic system optimisation and these will have to be resolved.

Firstly, the lecturer has to continuously engage in continuous self-development. There must be a concerted effort to ensure that the knowledge and capacity base of the lecturer is up-to-date at every point in time. This is to enable them to have new knowledge to impact their students. Attending professional development and learning activities such as online and in-person conferences, workshops, seminars, and all other such

academic engagements are avenues for obtaining fresh insights. Quite, unfortunately, not very many academics get support funding to attend such engagements. Those who attempt to do so, do this at the peril of their already very meagre remuneration. The issue of poor remuneration does not only dampen the morale of lecturers in the system already but also discourages potential bright students with the requisite capacity to deliver on the university education mandate. Also note that basic infrastructural facilities such as electricity and internet connectivity are scarce, leaving many willing academics without access to the required resources leading to untold levels of frustration, confusion and sometimes depression. This plight of University lecturers has hindered progress in research and scholarship in specialised areas of endeavours where developmental ideas emanate (Ndayebom & Aregbesola, 2024; Somadina et al, 2024).

Secondly, there is the need to alter the prevailing pedagogy. It is important to obtain degrees and master the theory and principles of the subject matter. However, there are a lot of abstract concepts being taught in isolation. A new pedagogy should use approaches that transcribe abstract concepts into concrete phenomena by using pictures, short movies or any form of dramatisation that will enable students get to a better understanding of how abstract knowledge can solve concrete problems. This the lecturer should be able to achieve through the support of Institutional policymakers.

Thirdly, as part of trying to teach practicals in the universities, a lecturer should be encouraged to have practice centres and also engage in corporate activities. This is a way of getting firsthand information about what happens in real-life situations at the time and also practising what he or she preaches which exposes the students to practical live scenarios. This also gives better explanations of the theories and principles being taught in real organisational settings. Lecturers could be given the opportunity from time to time to take up working opportunities in the industry apart from conferences and workshops where they could interact with industry specialists. University lecturers are allowed to go on sabbatical once in seven years. This may be the only opportunity to gain real firsthand experience and may not be enough in the contemporary contexts of volatility, uncertainty, complexity, and ambiguity in which firms operate.

Also, some lecturers’ unwillingness to learn is another debilitating issue. The persons vehemently still stick to dogmatic myopic views which they usually would want to impose on other lecturers and students. These set of persons are sometimes in the hegemonic minority who display megalomaniac possession of pseudo-knowledge. They are usually not open to constructive critiquing, their ego is easily bruised and lack the willingness to accept novel ideas. Lecturers are expected to update their knowledge and skills often to impact positively the lives and skills of the students

and make meaningful contributions to knowledge. Embracing technology and digital tools as well as other novel research and teaching methods can enhance student engagement, make them better equipped to tackle future workplace challenges, research and collaboration as well as foster advancements in theories and practices. It is important to state that the passion to teach and learn is personal. Although this can be encouraged and inculcated, the onus ultimately lies on the individual lecturer or student to grow their passion that will drive the delivery and acquisition of course instructions for the particular subject area. This passion can drive the individual to unimagined heights of contributions or achievements. Students could be introduced to the research process as early as the first year of study. The building of research interest is to make students grow a passion for the investigation of phenomena and problem-solving in their areas of specialisation.

Employees will exhibit desirable behaviours if they perceive they have the necessary support. For example, if lecturers believe that their universities and the government place a high value on them by caring for their welfare and well-being and providing a conducive working environment, they are likely to be engaged, committed and perform tasks enthusiastically that will enhance the academic system optimisation drive. University leadership behaviours, working conditions in terms of pay, fairness and other human resource practices; research funding, sponsorship of career development opportunities; workload consideration, as well as the availability of basic infrastructure for teaching the opportunities are factors that may also be looked at to get the desired optimisation levels.

THE INSTITUTIONAL POLICYMAKERS AS STAKEHOLDERS

The university management and the National Universities Commission are two, among other, key institutions saddled with the responsibility of making policies that govern academic programmes, which this work focuses on. The acquisition and application of knowledge are for the enhancement of national distinctive competencies, competitive advantage, and global economic benefits. The need for the development of unique standard practices in the different fields of specialisation has been subject to several challenges. Despite many policies, which have sometimes been seen as conflicting, the issue of having an academic system that optimises the goals of the policies to use the knowledge obtained from the universities to solve socioeconomic and sociopolitical challenges amongst several other desirable expectations has not been achieved. The Nigerian educational model emphasises that the curriculum for the undergraduate programme, which is usually for a minimum of four years, lays a foundation to obtain problem-solving skills in both theoretical and practical knowledge cases. A major shortcoming of many of the institutional

policies of the universities and government policies is that the pedagogical considerations of course contents in the various academic fields in Nigerian universities are a hybrid of borrowed courses in line with the Western curriculum with a few courses unique to the Nigerian socio-cultural environment. The courses are introduced without recourse to the training of staff to teach in the required capacity and to deliver on other logistics. Also, there is a dire need to come up with context-specific strategies and to use specialised knowledge to intervene in national and global challenges noting her specific cultural, socioeconomic and sociopolitical uniqueness. These points have also been noted in extant literature.

The various categorisations of the Nigerian educational system into Federal Government, State Government or privately owned universities all work in line with the dictates of the National Universities Commission which prescribes a uniform Core Curriculum and Minimum Academic Standards (CCMAS). There are several issues that policymakers will have to address if the academic system is to make the needed impact for knowledge enhanced and transformed into meaningful societal benefits.

One big issue to be considered is the syndrome of ‘putting the cart before the horse’. Several policies would have been more beneficial to the system if they were sequentially done. For example, Institutions have courses with contents with learning outcomes that enable students to employ the use of technology to improve tasks, and virtual learning environments as well as encourage Innovation. The public schools have limited technologically enhanced learning facilities such as interactive software, online access, multimedia devices, and resources to engage them in hands-on learning techniques. Also, lecturers and students have limited access to up-to-date data to make informed decisions. A policy for the compulsory study of courses based on technological aids should not be without basic infrastructures for its study as well as the employment of staff for that purpose. The issues of infrastructural deficiencies as well as insufficient funds for research and innovation to meet lecturers’ and students’ expectations are well documented in extant literature (Abubakar et al,2025; Aliye,2019; Becheikh et al, 2022; Gyang & Maton, 2025; Ngoasong, 2022). If this keeps happening, the academic system’s advancement will be hampered by the prevalence of square pegs in round holes.

Also, wrong policies on what constitutes the content of courses, who teaches them, what courses are domiciled in what programme become an object of debate due to the pecuniary or egoistic benefits of such courses rather than focusing on an acceptable standard of best practices for the ultimate benefits of the students For example where a course is domiciled could be a function of the hegemonic composition of the policymakers drafting the allocation of courses to programmes at that given time. Maduagwu and Otusinkama, (2024) have identified the shortcomings of

political involvement in innovation in curriculum. Policies made without proper consideration of the situational context for teaching and learning are very discouraging and frustrating for both lecturers and students. This has resulted in brain drain syndrome where persons who have more favourable opportunities leave the system. The mental health of those who remain are adversely affected which further worsens the situation. The curriculum still falls short of industry standards. Insufficient emphasis is placed on experiential learning and real-world application. Budding entrepreneurs have little access to Institutional funds and support. Institutions should intently look into the policy concerns raised in this paper to mitigate the challenges.

Clear evidence that institutional policies are providing the necessary support for other stakeholders may include students' success in academics and their careers, increased student and lecturer attraction, satisfaction and retention, and positive research output from lectures and students as well as high ranking and positive reviews on the university's reputation. The organisations' climate, employee home-work programmes, career development opportunities, access to tools and learning aids, social norms, as well as progressive corporate structures and cultures are some other positive stakeholder support avenues.

PROFESSIONAL BODIES AS STAKEHOLDERS

Professional organisations' interactions help exchange ideas and emphasise the necessity of innovation and ongoing development in Academic systems. In some cases, the demands and expectations of the corporate world and its shifting dynamics are made known in professional conferences and meetings. The outcomes of such meetings can prompt the drawing up of a curriculum that will specify the industry needs of the different specialised areas of study. Such professional observations in the knowledge gap of graduates from universities could prompt the professional bodies' advisory role to policymakers (Ebekozien et al, 2024; Familoni & Shoetan, 2024). Professional bodies also control the professional members and recommend sanctions that erring members can face. This compels students and lecturers in the professional area to strictly adhere to professional codes of conduct, maintain optimum standards and ensure best practices. However, membership in some professional bodies by persons in academia is largely voluntary and sanctions by such bodies on members that err against their professional ethics or codes of conduct are either not clear or are nonexistent. Professional bodies should emphasise their roles not just in upholding the tenets of their areas of specialisation but as responsible agents that enforce standards for the safety, well-being and progress in society (Fajimi, 2025; Itua et al, 2024). Professional bodies should do more to regulate professional practices at the point of training within the universities to optimise the system while also having

actionable sanctions to tighten the noose on transgressors in actual practice.

SOCIETY AS STAKEHOLDERS

University education has a lot to contribute to society in terms of individual and corporate ethical practices, good governance, social responsibility, accountability and so on. However, the issues affecting the optimisation of the academic system cannot be isolated from the prevalent issues which are peculiar to the sociopolitical, socioeconomic and sociocultural situations in the contextual environment. Nwachukwu and Azuka (2024) posit that as a transformative tool, education has a lot to do with the progress and development of a nation. The mental readiness required for learning has been adversely affected by societal ethos. Placing graduate unemployment level and the social expectations and regard for wealth side by side, people will rather believe that one does not need a university degree to be wealthy and seek other alternatives. This scenario that depicts an apparent societal devaluation of education makes young people perceive education as a scam (Bamidupe, 2024; Ezeani, 2024). Thus, some students' lacklustre attitude towards the academic rigours required to acquire and contribute to knowledge if there are no immediate economic benefits.

It is also observed that some university graduates are unable to strictly adhere to the principles and theories of their profession and are often faced with compelling dilemmas as social norms tend to contradict academic knowledge. For example, instances of nepotism and tribalism could sometimes override meritocracy in practical work situations which negates academic principles but runs contrary to societal dictates.

As part of the teaching component of the lecturer's duties, there should be a continuous student orientation about the usefulness of university education to personal life, career, society and academia.

The prevailing contemporary dictates of society have greatly influenced the behavioural disposition of some students towards the level of importance they attach to their academic programmes. Students are confused about being taught something in schools which negates what society dictates. Actionable steps should be taken to stem this trend. On one hand, students should be exposed to what obtains in real life and not just how things ought to be done. Pragmatic pedagogies that encourage practical problem-solving can be introduced rather than fixating on abstract and sometimes unrealistic ideas or rules. Practical methodology in teaching as a way forward having investigated the challenges of teaching and learning in African settings has been variously discussed (Abasilim et al, 2025; Mbonambi et al, 2023; Ukhurebor et al, 2025). On the other hand and as a follow-up measure, the minds of students should be built to stand firm and be resilient in the implementation of management

theories and principles learnt in school while taking situational decisions in the actual workplace. A concerted effort to contend with negative societal forces can be won this way.

METHODOLOGY

This paper examines the issues militating against academic systems based on participant observation as well as systematic desk research where the issues were treated in themes. The contextual environment took cognisance of public universities in Nigeria.

CONCLUSION

With the convergent effects of globalisation, and the growing significance of knowledge as a primary driver of growth, the application and accumulation of knowledge, especially at the university level, are now vital to a nation's ability to compete in the global economy. The mutually beneficial interaction between theory and practice positions university academic systems as national change agents. Effective academic systems have a direct impact on economic performance by boosting production, dedication to responsiveness and quality in efficiency, health care and the strategic deployment of resources, social well-being and other areas are vital to having a generally functional society for the advancement of the country. The academic systems and the stakeholders, which include students, lecturers, institutional policymakers, professional bodies, and society, cannot be treated separately as they influence one another and must work as a composite whole for the optimisation of the public universities' academic system and national development to be achieved. Addressing the interrelated issues raised in this study holistically is necessary if the much-anticipated benefits of academic system efficiency are to be achieved.

REFERENCES

1. Abasilim, C. F., Onyewuchi, I. V., & Inya, M. U. (2025). Exploring the nexus of agripreneurial mindset, education, and passion in Nigerian agricultural science students. *Covenant Journal of Entrepreneurship*, 9(1), 23-32.
2. Abdullahia, N. J. K. (2025). Entrepreneurship skills and sustainable development: the moderator effect of education quality management. *Journal of Sustainable Development Innovations*, 2(1), 8-22.
3. Abubakar, U., Onasanya, S. A., Aliyu, H. I., & Abdulrahman, M. R. (2025). Reimagining edupreneurship with AI technologies: Pathways to modern educational excellence in Nigerian tertiary institutions. *Ilorin Journal of Education*, 45(2), 222-236.
4. Ajayi, S. O. (2024). Infrastructure facilities, academic staff job performance and students academic performance in tertiary institutions in Nigeria. *American Journal of Alternative Education*, 1(1), 1-7.
5. Akinyemi, I. A., & Mohammed, M. O. B. (2023). Achieving national sustainable development through educational planning and administration in Nigeria: The harsh reality. *African Journal of Educational Management, Teaching and Entrepreneurship Studies*, 9(1), 60-75.
6. Aliye, A. A. (2019). The challenges of management research in Africa: A study of selected Ethiopian higher education institutions. *African Journal of Business Management*, 13(14), 456-464.
7. Asiyai, R. I. (2022). Best practices for quality assurance in higher education: implications for educational administration. *International Journal of Leadership in Education*, 25(5), 843-854.
8. Bamidu, A. E. (2024). The true enemies of Nigeria vis-a viz the 2023's general elections: A hermeneutical approach. *Oracle of Wisdom Journal of Philosophy and Public Affairs*, 8(1), 12-23.
9. Becheikh, N., Mourad, M., & Tolba, A. (2022). Promoting case-based learning in business higher education in the Middle East and North Africa region. *Journal of Management Education*, 46(4), 778-808.
10. Ebekozi, A., Aigbavboa, C. O., Adekunle, S. A., Aliu, J., & Thwala, W. D. (2024). Training needs of built environment professionals: The role of fourth industrial revolution. *Engineering, Construction and Architectural Management*, 31(11), 4353-4371.
11. Edokpolor, J., Otache, I., & Osifo, K. (2022). Work self-efficacy and engagement of vocational business education lecturers. *Journal of Technical Education and Training*, 14(3), 112-124.
12. Eli-Chukwu, N. C., Igbokwe, I. C., Ifebude, B., Nmadu, D., Iguodala, W., Uma, U., Onyeneke, R & Akudo, F. U. (2023). Challenges confronting e-learning in higher education institutions in Nigeria amid COVID-19. *Journal of Applied Research in Higher Education*, 15(1), 238-253
13. Ezeani, C. C. (2024). CHATGPT: Impact on academic research and education in Nigeria. *Nigerian Journal of African Studies*, 6(1), 1-8.
14. Fajimi, B. A. (2025). Roles of social workers in bridging the gap between social policy and social action in youth unemployment in Nigeria. *American Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities*, 10(1), 30-46.
15. Familoni, B. T., & Shoetan, P. O. (2024). Cybersecurity in the financial sector: a comparative analysis of the USA and Nigeria. *Computer Science & IT Research Journal*, 5(4), 850-877.
16. Goga, Y. M., Bashir, B. I., & Aliyu, I. A. (2023). Effect of emotional exhaustion on workplace deviant behaviour among academic staff: The role

- of affective commitment. *International Journal of Intellectual Discourse*, 6(3), 166-177.
17. Gyang, L., & Maton, S. (2025). Impact of students' population growth on educational infrastructure provided by the Plateau State University, Bokkos, Nigeria. *Plasu Journal of Environmental Sciences*, 1(1),145-154.
 18. Hoo, W. C., Wen, S. S., Ibrahim, F., & Madhavedi, S. (2024). Impact of self-efficacy, self-esteem, employee engagement, and organizational citizenship behaviour on job performance of academic staff in higher education institutions of Klang Valley, Malaysia. *Educational Administration: Theory and Practice*, 30(5), 9628-9649.
 19. Ilonze, G. U. (2024). Stress management and performance of public university lecturers in South East Nigeria. *American Research Journal of Contemporary Issues*, 2(1), 24-44.
 20. Itua, E. O., Bature, J. T., & Eruaga, M. A. (2024). Pharmacy practice standards and challenges in Nigeria: A comprehensive analysis. *International Medical Science Research Journal*, 4(3), 295-304.
 21. Jacob, N. (2024). Challenges and recommendations in administration Teacher Education: A Nigerian perspective. *Journal of Applied Science and Social Science*, 14(3), 1-7.
 22. JAMB (2024).Joint Admissions and Matriculation Board. Registrar’s Report on 2023 ADMISSION & 2024 UTME. Final report 18 July_2024.
 23. Laiho, A., Jauhiainen, A., & Jauhiainen, A. (2022). Being a teacher in a managerial university: Academic teacher identity. *Teaching in Higher Education*, 27(2), 249-266.
 24. Maduagwu, U. M., & Otusinkama, L. (2024). Influence of politics in curriculum innovation and change in Nigeria educational system. *African Journal of Educational Management, Teaching and Entrepreneurship Studies*, 11(2), 90-103.
 25. Mbatha, N., Satimburwa, N., Msiza, V., & Zonal, T. (2020). The academentia of ECAs: Navigating academic terrain through critical friendships as a life jacket. *Educational Research for Social Change*, 9(SPE), 31-44. <https://dx.doi.org/10.17159/2221-4070/2020/v9i2a3>.
 26. Mbonambi, T. R., Gamede, B. T., & Ajani, O. A. (2023). Investigating the challenges of teaching and learning business studies in South African rural high schools: in pursuit of enhanced classroom practices. *Multicultural Education Journal*, 9(2), 31-44.
 27. Mohammed, A., Ibitoye, O., & Haruna, H. (2024). Pedagogical skills, self-efficacy and content knowledge need for shorthand instructional delivery of lecturers in public tertiary institutions in Niger State, Nigeria. *Indonesian Journal of Education and Social Sciences*, 3(1), 1-16.
 28. Musa, H., Yusha'u, B., & Adam, M. (2024). Investigating computer science education students' and lecturers' awareness and self-efficacy for mobile learning in tertiary institutions in Bauchi State Nigeria. *ATBU Journal of Science, Technology and Education*, 12(2), 310-318.
 29. Ndayebom, A. J., & Aregbesola, B. G. (2024). Problems facing research programme in Nigerian tertiary institutions. *European Journal of Higher Education and Academic Advancement*, 1(2), 290-299.
 30. Ngoasong, M. Z. (2022). Curriculum adaptation for blended learning in resource-scarce contexts. *Journal of Management Education*, 46(4), 622–655.
 31. Nwachukwu, E. L., & Azuka, C. V. (2024). Education and character reformation in Nigeria contemporary society: Challenges and prospects. *Journal of Digital Learning and Distance Education*, 2(12), 879-887
 32. NUC (2024). National Universities Commission. Monday Bulletin, 19(17), 1-22. <https://www.nuc.edu.ng>
 33. Oderinde, S. L., Akintunde, O. Y., & Ajala, I. R. (2024). A critical analysis of the impact of work overload on lecturers' well-being: A case of Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile-Ife, Nigeria. *International Journal of Qualitative Research*, 3(3), 238-249.
 34. Ogunode, N. J., & Ade, T. I. (2023). Research programme in public universities in Nigeria. *Best Journal of Innovation in Science, Research and Development*, 2(3), 1-13
 35. Omoniyi, T. O. (2024). Potential graduates' knowledge, readiness, and disposition to 21st century employability skills in the University of Ibadan, Ibadan Nigeria. *Dynamic Multidisciplinary Journal*, 4(1)144-157.
 36. Osilike, C. C., Ogochukwu, E. C., & Okechukwu, A. E. (2024). Managing workplace stress in adult education lecturers: The efficacy of mindfulness-based intervention. *Mindfulness*, 15(4), 844-856.
 37. Somadina, O. I., Ayo, V. A., & Ayoko, V. O. (2024). Research development in public universities in Nigeria: Problems and solutions. *European Journal of Higher Education and Academic Advancement*, 1(1), 83-94.
 38. Ukhurebor, K. E., Egenti, G., & Uduehi, I. (2025). Contemporary approaches to science and engineering pedagogy: A perspective from Nigerian engineering education. *Journal of Infrastructure, Policy and Development*, 9(1),1-11.
 39. Uyeri, A. (2024). Workplace well-being: An analysis of lecturers' mental and emotional well-being in relation to their academic productivity.

GPH-International Journal of Educational Research, 7(1), 48-64.

40. Yang, S., Shu, D., & Yin, H. (2022). Teaching, my passion; publishing, my pain: Unpacking academics’ professional identity tensions through the lens of emotional resilience. *Higher Education*, 84(2), 235-254.